

Safety Analysis of SMR with PAssive Mitigation strategies - Severe Accident

Deliverable 2.2 iPWR input-deck and scenarios analyses

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Abstract

The HORIZON-EURATOM SPSAM-SA project, coordinated by ENEA (Italy), was launched in 2022 aiming at filling this gap and at transferring the knowledge and know-how of large LWR to integral PWRs (iPWRs) in view of the European licensing needs with respect to Severe Accident (SA) and Emergency Planning Zone (EPZ). One of the goals of the project is the evaluation of the capabilities of state-of-art European and non-European integral codes to properly predict the key phenomena occurring in postulated SA scenarios in two generic (but representative) iPWRs. Note that such generic reactor concepts include the main iPWR design features considered in the most promising designs in the European market.

Having this in mind, a large working activity has been performed in the frame of the WP2 (SCENARIO) by the SASPAM-SA partners aiming at the assessment of the datasets of the most used integral codes in Europe (ASTEC, MELCOR, AC2, EDF-MAAP, and MAAP) for the generic iPWRs considered in the project, the postulation of Design Basis Accident (DBA) and SA scenarios for such systems, and the corresponding calculation campaign. Furthermore, the ANSYS CFX and the containmentFOAM models have been assessed and transient analyses have been performed.

The current report focusses on the description of the work activity performed in the WP2, with particular focus on the evaluation of the capabilities of the integral codes employed by the partners to describe the behaviour of the two selected iPWR Designs during both the postulated DBA and SA scenarios. The ASTEC, MELCOR, AC2, EDF-MAAP, and MAAP results of the key figure-of-merits are compared and a quite extensive survey of the capabilities of the code to simulate the most relevant phenomena, e.g., thermal-hydraulics, core degradation, activation of the passive systems, characterizing generic iPWRs designs.

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1 Introduction

Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) are one of the innovative Nuclear Power Plants (NPP) to be deployed in the near-term worldwide. In Europe, the technological and economical interest for SMRs has been growing for some years. Activities are going on in several member states aiming at supporting the licensing of such systems. Among the different concepts, the Integral Pressurized Water Reactors (iPWRs) are of particular interest. They are ready to be licensed as new builds, since they integrate several evolutionary features, particularly of a passive nature, to enhance even further the already inherent safety. In spite of the advantageous impact of passive safety systems on the first three levels of the Defence-in-Depth (DiD) approach, a systematic demonstration of iPWR ability to prevent and to manage Severe Accidents (SA) needs to be done (DiD levels 4-5) [1, 2]¹.

In order to fill this gap, the HORIZON-EURATOM 'Safety Analysis of SMR with PASSive Mitigation strategies - Severe Accidents' (SASPAM-SA) project, coordinated by ENEA (Italy), was launched in 2022 and takes the contribution of 23 partners from 13 European countries [3-6]. The main objective of the SASPAM-SA project is to investigate the applicability and transfer of knowledge and know-how accumulated on the operating large-LWR reactors to the iPWRs. These activities are performed in view of European licensing needs relevant to SA and Emergency Planning Zone (EPZ) analyses. SASPAM-SA therefore aims at investigating the key elements to create a European independent point of view on the safety of iPWRs with respect to DiD levels 4 and 5 [1, 2, 3]. The expected project's outcome is to support and speed-up the licensing and siting process of iPWRs in Europe. The pillars of the SASPAM-SA project are topics not addressed in other on-going iPWR initiatives. In particular, the determination of the conditions prevailing in the Reactor Pressure Vessel (RPV) and containment under postulated SA scenarios is an essential element to support any other ongoing investigation within the project.

Two generic design-concepts are considered in SASPAM-SA. The iPWR Design 1 is characterized by a submerged containment and electric power of ~60 MWe and the iPWR Design 2 of ~300 MWe, which employs several passive systems and a dry containment. Note that it is not the project's objective to assess the design of such concepts. One of the primary goals of SASPAM-SA is the evaluation of the capabilities of integral SA codes and Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) tools to simulate the key phenomena occurring in generic iPWR designs. There are differences between iPWRs and the running reactors fleet, like the tighter interaction between the different systems of iPWRs (e.g., primary, containment, and safety systems), which might question the capability of the integral codes to predict such strong thermal-hydraulic (TH) coupling. To name a few: single and two-phase natural circulation in integral RPV, thermal stratification in large pools, primary/containment coupling, in-vessel melt retention, etc. [7-10].

The current report focusses on describing and discussing the results of the activities conducted within the second Work Package of the project (WP2) with focus on:

1. the assessment of generic, but representative, SA and CFD codes' datasets,
2. the analysis of the behavior of the generic iPWR designs during hypothetical postulated DBA and SA scenarios,

¹ Advanced designs, as iPWRs, are in general characterized by common features with the current operating large-LWR and by other specific features typical of their inherent evolutionary designs, providing safety advantages that reinforce the first three levels of the DiD principle. However, even if a plant is designed with advanced inherent features (through the reinforcement of the 1,2,3 DiD levels) allowing a reduction of the Core Damage Frequency (CDF), independent features for preventing and mitigating a severe accident sequence have to be included in its design (DiD level 4) together with the offsite emergency response (DiD level 5). Therefore, some scenarios that could lead to severe accidents need to be postulated and deterministically studied. More detailed information's in [1].

3. the assessment of the codes' capability to simulate the dominant phenomena driving the accident scenarios and in particular to reproduce the behavior of the different passive safety systems and their interactions in a SMR configuration.

For each iPWR design, a set of DBA and SA scenarios are postulated and analyzed. Note that since no Probabilistic Safety Analysis (PSA) assessments are done (generic designs are considered), SA scenarios are selected in terms of severity and not of probability to occur. In order to analyze code capability in a wider way the following passive systems have been considered in the work activity: passive decay heat removal; primary automatic depressurization; passive high-pressure safety injection, passive low pressure safety injection, containment pressure suppression, passive flooding of reactor cavity. Furthermore, in the frame of the project, the WP2 has the task to provide the necessary input and boundary conditions to be employed in the activities planned in the other WPs. The next sections describe the progress made so far in this venture.

2 The generic iPWR Design-1 and Design-2

The generic iPWR Design-1 and Design-2 considered in the SASPAM-SA project are shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2. The specifications of both designs were determined in the WP2 based on open literature and engineering judgment [11]. Such generic reactor concepts include the main iPWR design features considered in the most promising designs in the European market. Therefore, their employment in the project aims to assess more broadly the capability of codes (SA and CFD) to simulate the phenomena typical of iPWR.

The generic iPWR Design-1 reactor (Figure 1) investigated here consists of a natural circulation iPWR composed of a shrouded reactor core and riser, an integrated Pressurizer (PRZ), and a Helical coil Steam Generator (HSG) within an integral RPV housed inside a steel containment. The containment is largely immersed in a large pool of water, serving as the ultimate heat sink. The Emergency Core Cooling System (ECCS) in the iPWR Design-1 consists of two groups of valves allowing the coolant circulation between RPV and containment during accident conditions: the Reactor Vent Valves (RVV) located at the top of the PRZ and Reactor Recirculation Valves (RRVs) located slightly above the active core².

The iPWR Design-2 (Figure 2) is characterized by the use of several passive systems³ and by a dry containment. The reactor operates in forced circulation during normal operation and employs a passive mitigation strategy in accidental conditions. It consists of an integral RPV, containing the core, HSGs, primary pumps, the Control Rod Drive Mechanism (CRDM), and the PRZ. The hot water at the core outlet flows upwards in a circular riser up to the primary pumps suction located above each HSGs⁴.

As mentioned above, the objective of SASPAM-SA is not the assessment of the selected iPWR designs. On the contrary, the goal of the project is to investigate and prove the applicability of the state-of-art computation tools to reproduce SA conditions in generic iPWRs and identify code development needs.

² Even though Design-1 is generic, it includes some of the more evolutionary features of advanced SMR concepts, as integral RPV, compact SG, and natural circulation primary/containment coupling. More details on primary/containment coupling in a reactor with a submerged containment and the related experimental characterization, publicly available to the international community, are in [12].

³ Passive systems are, on the one hand, an advanced solution to increase the inherent safety of the plant (e.g., there is no need of pumps), on the other hand a) they require extensive investigation for assessing the functional failure related to the thermal-hydraulic phenomena driving the operation of the systems and assess the related uncertainties, b) may still need an active initiation, and c) are characterized by very limited operational experience (to have more detailed information [1,13]). Considering this, the impact of the operation of passive systems on postulated SA progression is a novel topic and needs to be assessed.

⁴ Considering the selected passive systems and the generic SMR features, a generic IRIS-SMR type has been considered as reference for this analysis (no proprietary data have been used); therefore, the main geometric information has been determined by scaling the data available from the SPES-3 facility, by engineering evaluation or public general data available from the IRIS reactor [14].

Figure 1: Layout of the iPWR Design-1 generic reactor concept.

Figure 2: Layout of the iPWR Design-2 generic reactor concept.

3 Development of the datasets of integral and CFD codes

The activities performed by the partners have been organized based on the following tasks:

1. Assessment of a common database for the iPWR Design-1 and Design-2 based on open literature to assess the iPWRs datasets;
2. Development of integral plant input decks of the two iPWR designs (SA and CFD codes);
3. Identification and analyses of DBA and SA sequences for the two iPWR designs;
4. Evaluation of a database of nuclear inventory vs. burn-up of the iPWR designs.

The full list of the partners and of the integral and CFD codes employed are given in Table 1 and Table 2 for the iPWR Design-1 and Design-2, respectively. The reference European and non-European computational tools are employed in the WP2 of the SASPAM-SA project. In order to increase the efficiency of the planned activities, some partners joined the project by sharing their own datasets, upon request. Such novel approach allowed a sensible acceleration in fulfilling the above-mentioned tasks 2 and 3, in particular. As shown in Table 1 and Table 2, Tractebel and PSI made available the ASTECv2.2 and MELCORv2.2 datasets, respectively, of the iPWR Design-1.

Similarly, ENEA and ENEA/UNIROMA1 made available the ASTECv3.1 and MELCORv2.2 datasets, respectively, of the iPWR Design-2. Furthermore, IRSN and GRS, as ASTEC and AC2 developers, respectively, supported the users. New datasets of the EDF-MAAP and AC2 codes have been developed for the iPWR Design-1 by EDF and RUB, respectively. Similarly, for the iPWR Design-2, new datasets of the MAAPv5.06 and AC2 codes have been assessed by JRC and LEI, respectively. Concerning CFD codes, new datasets using ANSYS CFX and containmentFOAM were developed by SSTC NRS and FZJ for the iPWR Design-1 and Design-2, respectively.

Table 1. iPWR Design-1: Partners and codes, and contribution

Partner	Code	Comments
EDF	EDF-MAAP5.04	New dataset
GRS		Support to the AC2 Users
IRSN		Support to the ASTEC Users
KIT	ASTECv3.1	Contribution to a new dataset
KTH	MELCORv2.2	
PSI	MELCORv2.2	Sharing the dataset
RATEN		Support in the definition of the scenarios
RUB	AC2	New dataset
SSTC NRS	ANSYS CFX (CFD)	New dataset
Tractebel	ASTECv2.2/ASTECv3.1	Sharing the dataset

Table 2. iPWR Design-2: Partners and codes, and contribution

Partner	Code	Comments
CIEMAT	MELCORv2.2	
ENEA	ASTECv3.1/MELCORv2.2	Sharing the dataset
FZJ	CAD and containmentFOAM (CFD)	New dataset
GRS		Support to the AC2 Users
JRC	MAAPv5.06	New dataset
IRSN		Support to the ASTEC Users
KTH	MELCORv2.2	
LEI	AC2	New dataset
RATEN		Support in the definition of the scenarios
UNIROMA1	MELCORv2.2	Sharing the dataset

As an example of the CFD models developed, the ANSYS CFX model of the iPWR Design-1 in Figure 1 and the containmentFOAM model of the iPWR Design-2 are shown in Figure 3. ANSYS CFX (left, iPWR Design-1) and

containmentFOAM (right, iPWR Design-2) models mesh. (right). The ANSYS CFX model employs a preliminary mesh of about 370000 nodes for the initial round of calculations aimed at selecting and setting up the mathematical models to simulate thermal processes within the containment. Different containmentFOAM models have been developed, with preliminary meshes using between 200000 and 750000 cells for representing one quarter of the Desing-2 containment. Despite the analyses are still in progress, the preliminary results show rather stable simulations and a good qualitative assessment of the expected phenomenology.

Figure 3. ANSYS CFX (left, iPWR Design-1) and containmentFOAM (right, iPWR Design-2) models mesh.

4 Assessment of postulated accident scenarios

The performance of the integral codes in Table I and II to predict the key phenomena occurring during accidental phases for the selected iPWR designs has been investigated in two phases. First, a set of DBA scenarios has been identified for each design, to evaluate the capabilities of the codes to properly analyse the key TH phenomena in DBA conditions. In a second phase, SA scenarios have been selected to assess the code performance with respect to both TH and core degradation phenomena in SA conditions. It is worth to remind that the SA scenarios were identified based on the severity of the accident consequences and not in terms of probability, since no PSA assessments were carried out in the SASPAM-SA project.

4.1 Generic iPWR Design-1

Four DBA scenarios have been postulated for the generic iPWR Design-1 triggered by opening a break of different sizes (100%, 35%, 20%, and 10% pipe section) of an hypothetical Chemical and Volume Control System (CVCS) make-up line with loss of AC power supply. The CVCS discharge line is connected to the downcomer slightly above the top of the core. RRVs and RRVs are assumed available. The three SA scenarios postulated for the generic iPWR Design-1 are described as follows:

- SA-1: Break (100%) on the CVCS makeup line with loss of AC. RRVs are in operation. RRVs are postulated stuck closed;

- SA-2: Inadvertent opening (100%) of 1 RVV with loss of AC. Other RVVs are in operation. RRVs are postulated stuck closed;
- SA-3: Break (100%) on the venting line with loss of AC. RVVs are in operation. RRVs are postulated stuck closed.

4.2 Generic iPWR Design-2

One DBA scenario has been considered for the generic iPWR Design-2. The initiator is a guillotine break of one Direct Vessel Injection (DVI) line (Figure 1), while all the safety systems are available. The three SA scenarios postulated for the generic iPWR Design-2 are described as follows:

- SA-1: guillotine break of one DVI line, considering the unavailability of the Emergency Heat Removal System (EHRS) and Automatic Depressurization System (ADS)-1 (through the failure of correspondent valves to open);
- SA-2: guillotine break of one DVI line, considering the unavailability of all safety systems (through the not opening of the related valves);
- SA-3 (low pressure scenario): guillotine break of one DVI line and the unavailability of EHRS system (through the failure of correspondent valves to open).

4.3 Nuclide inventory and decay heat data

Depletion calculations have been performed for a representative 2D typical PWR fuel assembly of the iPWR Design-1 and Design-2 using CASMO5 lattice physics code, developed by Studsvik Scandpower [15, 16]. Decay heat data and isotopic inventories have been computed from 20 MWd/kgU to 60 MWd/kgU, with a burn-up step of 2.5 MWd/kgU. For the analyses, three sets of decay heat data were used: the set calculated in the WP2 [16], the 1973 ANS standard data, and the 1973 ANS standard data increased by 20%. The results show that after the scram, the WP2's decay power is about 30% lower than the 1973 ANS standard data.

5 Selected results of the postulated DBA and SA analyses

Selected results of the integral codes simulations of the postulated DBA and SA scenarios are shown in the subsections below. In agreement with the schedule of SASPAM-SA, since a systematic comparison among all the results is currently ongoing, attention is paid here to provide the description of the capabilities of the codes to predict the key phenomena occurring during the transients.

5.1 Generic iPWR Design-1: results of the DBA scenarios

The ASTECv2.2 results are here shown as a matter of example. The time dependent behaviour of the pressure in the RPV and in the containment computed by the code during the postulated DBA scenarios in the iPWR Design-1 is shown in Figure 4. The results have been obtained by using the 1973 ANS standard decay heat data increased by 20%. The opening of the break in the downcomer leads to a pressure drop in the RPV and a pressure increase in the containment, labelled with straight and dotted lines, respectively (Figure 4 left).

Figure 4. DBA scenarios: pressure in the RPV and in the containment (left) and water level (right) computed by ASTECv2.2.

The scenario initiated by the largest break size of the CVCS make-up line (100%) leads to a fast depressurization of the RPV and consequently to a large pressure increase containment up to about 55 bar. The scram occurs at about 4 s and the ECCS is activated at about 260 s triggering the recirculation phase and finally leading to equalize the pressure in the RPV and containment to less than 4 bar at the end of the transient. Smaller breaks of the CVCS make-up line (35%, 20%, and 10%) lead to slower initial pressure decrease in the RPV. In addition, since only part of the decay heat is removed through the break, there is a subsequent pressure increase in the RPV, which reaches a maximum before the ECCS activation. The peak pressure in the containment due to the ECCS intervention decreases as the size of the break decreases. However, once the ECCS is activated, the RPV pressure decreases up to the equalization with the containment at the same rate in all cases. From the phenomenological point of view, after the ECCS activation, the steam produced in the core travels along the ascending riser and exits through the RVVs; then the steam is condensed on the inner surface of the containment. The accumulated liquid at bottom of the containment is then returned to the RPV via RRVs. The energy from the containment is removed to the external pool which acts as ultimate heat sink. Figure 4 (right) shows, for the three different cases investigated, the liquid increase in the containment, and, when the ECCS valve opening, the refill of the core due to the gravity.

A preliminary comparison among the results obtained with the other integral codes used for the iPWR Design-1 (Table 1) shows a good qualitative and quantitative agreement on both pressure behaviours and ECCS activation time. In particular, for the DBA scenarios initiated by 100%, 35%, and 20% break, the deviation on the timing of the ECCS activation from the AC2, ASTEC, EDF-MAAP, and MELCORv2.2 codes ranges between 500-1000 s, while larger deviations are observed for the scenario induced by 10% break. A reasonable agreement among the codes is also observed on prediction of the values of the pressure peaks in the RPV and containment. The results show that the codes are able to predict the key TH phenomena during DBA scenarios (e.g., single and two-phase natural circulation in integral RPV, primary/containment natural circulation coupling, energy removal from the external pool, etc.).

5.2 Generic iPWR Design-1: results of the SA-1 scenario

The ASTECv3.1 results concerning the key events and parameters during the progression of the SA-1 scenario, are shown in Table 3. The calculations were performed using the decay data computed in the WP2 (task 2.4, [16]), the 1973 ANS standard data (ANS73 in Table 3), and the 1973 ANS standard data increased by 20% (ANS73+20% in Table 3). As expected, the higher the decay heat, the faster the progression of the core degradation. The time at which the Fission Products (FP) are released ranges from 6664 s to 9099 s, and the

instant of the first slump of corium into the lower plenum ranges from 21069 s to 25189 s. Finally, the total mass of corium relocated in the lower plenum varies from 5.7 tons to 10.6 tons.

Table 3. Progression of the postulated SA-1 scenario (ASTECv3.1) against decay heat data

Key events/parameters	Task2.4 [15]	ANS73	ANS73 +20%
Scram time [s]	4.3	4.3	4.3
ECCS signal [s]	934.1	933.1	950.6
Max. containment pressure [MPa]	2.65	2.75	2.81
Start of FPs release from fuel pellets [s]	9099.7	7925.8	6664.9
First material slump in the lower plenum [s]	12159.7	10725.8	9064.9
First slump of corium with FPs in the lower plenum [s]	25189.7	23850.8	21069.9
First total core uncover [s]	32200.7	31105.8	22435.4
Total H2 mass produced in the vessel [kg]	64	58.6	60.8
Final H2 mass in the containment [kg]	53.9	48.9	51.3
Final aerosols mass in the containment [kg]	329.2	196	184
Total corium relocation in the lower plenum [kg]	5771	9495	10638

A preliminary comparison of the results from the different integral codes employed shows a reasonable agreement on some figure-of-merits. No RPV failure is predicted by the codes for any of the postulated SA scenarios. Going back to the SA-1 scenario, when using the same decay heat data, the deviation of the predicted time of the beginning of the material relocation to the lower plenum is about 1,000 s. Furthermore, the maximum deviation of the total amount of corium relocated to the lower plenum is about 1 ton. Finally, concerning the in-vessel hydrogen production, the deviation among the code predictions is ~20 kg.

As an example, selected EDF-MAAP5.04 and ASTECv3.1 results for the SA-1 obtained by employing the 1973 ANS standard decay data increased by 20% are shown in Figure 4. The results relevant to the hydrogen produced in the RPV (Figure 4, left) show some deviations on the instant at which the phenomenon starts (~5,500 s in ASTECv3.1 and ~7,800 s in EDF-MAAP5.04) and on the total amount of hydrogen produced (~20 kg), the latter looking mainly due different approaches to model the oxidation of stainless-steel components in the core. Further investigations on the source of such deviation are currently going-on. The EDF-MAAP5.04 and ASTECv3.1 results concerning the material relocation in the lower plenum (Figure 4, right) show a reasonable agreement on both the total mass of corium and oxidic pool.

Figure 5. In-vessel hydrogen production (left) and total mass of corium and oxides relocated in the lower plenum (right) for the SA-1 computed by EDF-MAAP and ASTECv3.1.

5.3 Generic iPWR Design-2: results of the DBA scenario

The analysis of the DBA scenario in the iPWR Design-2 is rather challenging for integral codes since the system is equipped with several passive systems. The key events of the ASTECv3.1 simulation are shown in Table 4. The simulation was carried out for 100,000 seconds to include the main TH phenomena relevant in the scenario. The WP2 (Task 2.4, [16]) decay heat data were used. After the break, the transient is characterized by a fast decrease of the primary pressure and an increase of the containment pressure (Figure 6).

Table 4. Progression of the postulated DBA scenario (ASTECv3.1)

Event	Time [s]
Break	0
High containment pressure signal	20
SCRAM	25
EHRS loops opening	28
Low PRZ water level signal	65
RCP coast-down	80
Natural circulation begins through RI-DC valves	84
Low PRZ pressure signal	158
ADS Stage-1 opening	166
EBTs opening	160
Low DP RV-Containment	1398
LGMSs opening	1401
Low LGMS mass signal	12902

When the high containment pressure set-point is reached (20 s), the scram signal is activated, as well as the isolation of the secondary system, and the activation of the EHRS. The peak pressure in the secondary system is reached after some seconds (~120 bar) and quickly decreases (Figure 6– left) due to the heat removal from the Refuelling Water Storage Tank (RWST). When the low PRZ level set-point is reached (65 s), the reactor coolant pumps coast-down occurs, the riser-downcomer valves open, and the natural circulation in the RPV starts. The low-pressure set-point in the PRZ is reached at 122 s, triggering the activation of the first stage of the ADS and of the Emergency Borating Tanks (EBT), and leading to a rapid decrease of the primary and secondary pressure (Figure 6).

Figure 6. ASTECv3.1 prediction of the pressure in the PRZ, in the secondary system, and in the drywell (left) and water level in the cavity and core (right).

The low RPV-Containment Differential Pressure signal (1401 s), activated by the RPV and drywell (DW) pressures equalization, determines the opening of the valves connecting the Long term Gravity Make-up System (LGMS) line-B to the RPV (through the intact DVI line) and the LGMS line-A to the reactor cavity (RC)

(through the broken DVI line). Steam condensation on the containment walls and heat removal from the primary side due to the EHRS intervention causes the containment and the RPV pressure to decrease. When DW pressure decreases below the Pressure Suppression System (PSS) pressure, the PSS water is pushed inside the PSS vent pipes to the top end and fills the RC above the break level. When the LGMS mass reaches the low water mass signal, the ADS stage-2 valves are opened, permitting steam circulation between RPV and DW. During the long-term cooling phase, the core is kept filled and cooled by the water available from RC, the power is removed by the EHRS system, and the heat is evacuated to the environment through the DW metal surfaces. Figure 6 (right) shows the water level in the cavity and in the core predicted by ASTEC calculations. As for the results of the iPWR Design-1, a preliminary qualitative comparison among the predictions from the different integral codes employed for analysing the iPWR Design-2 is available. The results show a general agreement with respect to the timing of the activation of the safety systems and on the behaviour of some figure-of-merits, e.g., the pressure in the different compartments. On the other hand, the first important result is that all the codes have been able to predict most of the key thermal-hydraulic phenomena occurring in the scenario (e.g., single and two-phase natural circulation in integral RPV, behaviour of passive injection and heat removal systems, long term cooling, etc).

5.4 Generic iPWR Design-2: results of the postulated SA-1 scenario

The ASTECv3.1 results concerning the total hydrogen production in the RPV, the mass in the RPV, in the containment, and in the environment during the postulated SA-1 in the iPWR Design-1 (section 4.2) are shown in Figure 7 (left). Furthermore, the spatial distribution and the temperature of the molten material in the core before core relocation to the lower plenum are shown in Figure 7 (right). Calculations have been performed using the decay heat data computed in the frame of the activities of WP2.

Figure 7. Total mass of hydrogen in the RPV and in the containment (left) and temperature field in the RPV (right) at the end of the simulation in the SA-1 (ASTECv3.1).

The preliminary comparison of the results among the different integral codes employed in this task (Table II) shows a general qualitative agreement of the accident progression. The hydrogen production onset occurs between 1.5 and 2 h, and the core is uncovered at ~ 1 h after the beginning of the transient. Concerning the hydrogen production, the deviation among the codes' predictions is ~ 20 - 25% . Note that all the integral codes simulations show that no RPV lower head failure, due to the ex-vessel reactor cooling, and that the containment pressure design is reached. A deeper analysis and comparison of the results from the integral codes is currently ongoing in the framework of the SASPAM-SA WP2.

6 Conclusion

The HORIZON-EURATOM SASPAM-SA project, coordinated by ENEA (Italy), was launched in 2022 to investigate the application of the multi-decade knowledge accumulated on operating large LRW reactors to iPWRs, in view of supporting the European license needs relevant to SA and EPZ. Within the project framework, WP2, managed by KIT (Germany), focuses on developing input deck, assessing hypothetical DBA and SA scenarios, and performing the corresponding analyses. This involves utilizing widely adopted state-of-the-art European and non-European integral codes, along with CFD tools, to analyse postulated DBA and SA scenarios in two generics but representative iPWRs. Such systems incorporate key safety features characteristic of the most promising iPWR designs poised for entry into the European market. The main goal is to evaluate the capabilities of the target codes to predict the main phenomena characterizing the iPWRs in accident conditions.

In the framework of the WP2, DBA and SA scenarios have been postulated, the SA scenarios being assessed based on their severity and not on PSA considerations. For the analyses, the integral codes are used. The corresponding models of the two generic designs employed in the project have been assessed by producing a common set of specifications based on open literature. The analyses indicate that the outcomes generated by various integral codes demonstrate both qualitative and quantitative consistency. Moreover, the results prove that the codes can simulate the fundamental phenomena observed during SAs in iPWRs.

Within WP2, such results are the basis for the development of CFD models for more detailed analysis of the containment phenomena in the postulated scenarios. The results of the integral and CFD codes' investigations represent, in the framework of the SASPAM-SA project, the boundary conditions for developing the other research activities planned in the project and focused on the identification of existing and needed key experiments for the iPWR assessment, the in-vessel melt retention, the containment behaviour, and the characterization of the EPZ.

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